

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Msina****FIRST NAME: Queen-Ruth****PROGRAM CODE: MIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied U.S. U.K. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. The preliminaries of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 5-12)
3. Style guide (EUCLID 2021, 24-25)
4. English versions (EUCLID 2021, 27)
5. Inflected Latin language (EUCLID 2021, 56-61)
6. Coursepack loopholes (EUCLID 2021, 1-4,27-28,30-32,38)

SKILL ENHANCEMENT FOR ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

As I grow older, I realize that I have huge interest in comprehensive knowledge as well as sharing it so as to benefit the general public. Not only that, but also, I have been exposed to educational institutions which use English as a main mode of instruction hence language did not seem like a barrier to me. My recent concern is, is my exposure to English language adequate to propel me forward in achieving my goal or is more polishing needed? Does my form and style match the matter in me? I must admit that it has been hard for me to initiate the writing of this response paper because I have been scared of making mistakes in grammar and maintaining the natural flow. I got highly motivated after reading *Teach Yourself to Express Yourself*, where it mentioned that” I think most successful writers would tell you that it is only after they have put pen to paper that they begin to examine critically what they have written in the light of lessons they may have learnt from the study of text-books or good models” (Jepson 1965, 2).

The review of ACA-401D Coursepack for Period 1 and tutorial videos have made me realize that i have multiple pitfalls in my writing skills that need filling up. The acquired skills have taught me to make a thesis statement and an argument by using solid evidence from relevant examples and information from reliable sources. I will express my attained knowledge while discussing key concepts from ACA-401 Period 1 Coursepack in the following paragraphs.

2) PRELIMINARIES OF ESSAY WRITING

The word essay originates from a French word *essais* which means “attempts” where the French philosopher Montaigne indicated it is an uncertain prose. He then added personal element to the tentative philosophical writings to create the modern *essay*. He additionally claimed that he is the groundwork of his book. Sober seriousness of purpose, dignity, logical organization, expository, argumentative and short discussion were termed as qualities of a formal essay. (Holman 1936, 204-205).

The assigned material in the Coursepack is in sync with the principles of personalization and argumentation as it suggests that arguing against oneself in making criticism is a great approach of taking an opinion seriously (EUCLID 2021, 22). The assigned guideline for writing a response paper encourages the use of personal nouns such as “I” and “me” (EUCLID 2021,3). Regardless of being personal, feelings are highly discouraged in for formal writing because the discussion is factual but emotions are fickle. I have been to multiple seminars and conference meetings where I have witnessed people who easily react rather than shock absorb being labeled as emotionally unintelligent.

ACA-401 Coursepack for Period 1 states than an evidence-based idea for persuasion of readers is the aim of writing academic essays and it should be from credible academic texts or credible sources. (EUCLID 2021, 1). Prior to collecting evidence, the Coursepack has emphasized on intense exploration on the topic at hand so that one can create a solid argument. After that, the answer to essay question should be decided upon in order to choose the information to use to respond to it (EUCLID 2021, 2).

3) PLAGIARISM

ACA-401 coursepack defined plagiarism as when a writer manipulates an author’s presentation and credits it as own’s work. Not only that, but it also warned that it is can result in serious academic consequences (EUCLID 2021, 5). I solidly agree with the study material in the academic package provided because the original writer has put in a lot of time, energy and resources to research a specific topic hence he/she deserves recognition for his/her work.

Stephen Marshall and Maryanne Garry did a research on attitudes and perceptions of plagiarism among English Speaking Background (ESB) and non-ESB (NESB) students. The study revealed that 83% and 65% of NESB and ESB students respectively practiced severe form of plagiarism. Generally, 4-11% did not consider copying words from another

source without referencing as plagiarism. They then concluded that all students should be trained on academic writing and ethical use of information from multiple sources (Marshall and Garry 2006, 32-34).

Based on the conclusion above, I have appreciated the fact that the Coursepack is serving its purpose by ensuring it is equipping me with all the tools that I need, in my introductory period. This educational set explains ways of citation depending on the source (EUCLID 2021, 6-12). I have gained a great deal of knowledge because I have a history of paraphrasing using the author's original words.

4) STYLE GUIDE

Consistent mode of documentation is to be maintained in order to preserve the style of a publication, company or website despite the contribution of more than one author. Chicago Rules (Turabian) is EUCLID's preference because it focuses on American English although other internationally accepted panaches and UK English are acceptable (EUCLID 2021, 24). I agree with this statement because every establishment has to have an identity which is incomparable to any other body. If everyone in an institution is capable of making his or her own decision regarding a matter, how chaotic is going to be?

I am also impressed with the flexibility of the course pack because despite insisting on constancy, it is not being judgmental towards the creative writers. It goes ahead to explain that nothing is wrong with them adopting their own style guide because they are expected to meet the demands of their clients of who have different taste. Nonetheless, it did not hesitate to comment on the gaps to be anticipated in freelancing whereby the writer is at a risk of reorganizing his or her work after realizing that it has similar flair to presentations in certain localities (EUCLID 2021, 25).

5) ENGLISH VERSIONS

Standard British English (SBE) and Standard American English (SAE) are the internationally recognized variants whereby they are held similar after they are collectively labeled as "educated" English. Based on detailed explanation on differences between SAE and SBE, the former is noted to mutate the original English words by differing in linguistic features such as pronunciation, spelling, grammar, syntax and punctuation. Not only that, but also, SAE is also sighted to add new strains of words in comparison to SBE due to high levels of creativity among its users so as to overcome social and cultural barriers. It is observed that in United States of America, there is 70% of native English speakers' population, reasons being its magnitude of higher education as well as its large publishing industry and mass media technology (EUCLID 2021, 27). The quoted word got me wondering, how sophisticated should a person be so as their English could be claimed "educated?" The *Concise Oxford Companion to the English Language* indicated that English speakers and writers who have completed secondary school are the targeted group.

I can relate with the above passage because I live in the busiest and most technological city in my country. The frequency and quality of usage of the respective language is so high compared to the rural areas. I believe it is a result of good exposure to foreigners who come into my town, which renders the city people obligated to learn it. Interestingly, speakers modify English words so often depending on the age group, profession and recent local event and geographical location. Also, most parents feel pressured to take their children to English medium schools because they want to maintain the continuity of the language for communication purposes.

6) INFLECTED LATIN LANGUAGE

Latin is an ancient language and it is not a native dialectal of any country at the present but it has been integrated into other modern languages including English.

Mouton stated that “speakers of British English have a generally relaxed attitude to loans in English, because the history of English is rarely taught in British schools, so they do not usually know that a particular word is a loan word unless their attention is drawn to a fact. Words of Latinate origin are often given high status by speakers and are typical of higher spoken language registers (and of formal written language)” (Mouton 2009, 370).

I second the author because I was not aware that all of the word and abbreviation examples, mentioned in the chapter 9 of period 1, have a Latin origin (EUCLID 2021, 56-61). Interestingly, these abbreviations that I use in my daily life are such as ante meridiem (A.M.), post meridiem (P.M.), curriculum vitae (c.v.), exempli gratia (e.g.), et cetera (etc.), id est (i.e.), nota bene (N.B.), post scriptum (P.S.), versus (v.), vice versa (v.v.) and viva (oral examination). Based on my profession as doctor, supra and infra are words I regularly use in reporting palpation and auscultation results such as “infrascapular” (below the scapula) and “suprapubic” (above the pubis) regions.

Not only that, but also, the inclusion of the topic in the presentation justifies the vitality of the language in the writing of official papers as Latin abbreviations are used in referencing methodology with a good example being et alia (et al.) (EUCLID 2021, 56-57). The latter example is used when source has four or more authors in in-text citations and eight or more authors in reference list or bibliography (in Chicago style). On the other hand, the Coursepack encouraged the use of plain English by stating that “Avoid jargon, acronyms, and abbreviations. Plain language should be visually inviting, logically organized and understandable on the first reading” (EUCLID 2021, 56).

7) COURSEPACK LOOPHOLES

a) Missing EUCLID guidelines in essay writing basics

I was worried when I started going through chapter one because the topic was reported to be from the University of New South Wales (UNSW) website for current

students (EUCLID 2021, 1-4). It got me wondering, does EUCLID have its own basic writing principles? However, I also noticed that coverage on that area was inadequate because there were missing tips from “Essay and Assignment Planning” postulate on the website. Other missing details were for “Effective Note-Making from Written Text” (EUCLID 2021, 2) and “guides on plagiarism and on various citation styles” (EUCLID 2021, 4).

On the other hand, I chose to understand that maybe UNSW basics of essay writing are in sync with the ones Euclid University prefer so they wanted to acknowledge the former institution for compiling the tremendous work.

b) Dormant hyperlinks

The assigned material has blue highlighted and underlined words and when clicked on them, they are expected to link me to another document for more clarification but to my surprise, they were inactive. As a result, I was obliged to manually copy and paste them to a browser for searching. Unfortunately, I happen to get multiple responses which get me confused on what exact link I should be looking into. The links are, “Are Americans ruining English” (EUCLID 2021,27), “ Harry Potter” and “example” (EUCLID 2021,28), “auto terms” and “ ‘Localization’ of Food Terms in Children’s Books” (EUCLID 2021,30), “Lost in Translation,” “The Twictionary,” “boingg,” and “WOTY2006”(EUCLID 2021,31), “death and funeral references,” “African Americans,” “Canola” and “niggardly”(EUCLID 2021,32), “Commonly Used Latin Expressions,” “Common Latin abbreviations Used in Writing,” “Related Technical Communication Information,” and “Jargon to avoid in scientific and technical writing” (EUCLID 2021,56). There are other two inactive hyperlinks on the footnotes of the 2nd page of the 2nd sample paper for correction (EUCLID 2021, 38).

c) Misspelling of the word ‘Coursepack’

Every time I type the word “Coursepack,” a red curly line appears underneath it implying that the word is wrongly spelled. On attempt for auto correction, the right word appears to be “Course pack”. I have not made any changes in my passage because it initially appeared like that in the assigned material and I have not been granted any permission to make changes to the name that carries the message of the academic package.

8) CONCLUSION

Reading the Coursepack has been eye opener to the features I took lightly. I have learnt to skim through important points that will enable me to answer a essay question. Furthermore, I also achieved knowledge on researching the topic from reliable sources so that collectively, I can arrange diverse ideas and write an evidence based presentation. I have also attained citing skills that have enabled me to put my sources in order without crediting them as my own. In addition to that, consistency has been motivated in my writing

by enhancing my style guiding. Proofreading via reading my passage out loud has been highlighted as the essential step for editing my essay.

Latin language has proven itself to me to be vital sources of origin for English words that I use in my daily life. The Coursepack's demonstrations have made me realize that Standard American English is a preference to me than the other variant and I am impressed that this specific taste matches the assigned material.

Lastly, I suggest that rejuvenation should be done on areas that revealed gaps so that the students that read it after me can render the source more reliable.

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